

PHILOLOGY

ABOUT THE CHTHONIC WORLD IN AZERBAIJANI FAIRY TALES: TIME AND SPACE

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Abstract

Azerbaijani fairy tales, deeply rooted in the rich cultural tapestry of the region, provide a fascinating glimpse into the collective imagination of the Azerbaijani people. This research article explores the chthonic world in Azerbaijani fairy tales, focusing on the intricate interplay of time and space. Through an analysis of Azerbaijani fairy tales, this study aims to unravel the cultural, historical, and symbolic dimensions embedded in these fairy tales, shedding light on how the Azerbaijani people perceive and conceptualize their world.

The study analyzes the structure of the chthonic world based on the aspect of space and time, system of space and time. Characters, forms and the diversity of the shape of the chthonic world are also analyzed: as the underground world, the chthonic world of the dead, thus concluding to the most important question of folklore research in the means of this theme — localization sites of chthonic world in the mythological worldview.

Keywords: chthonic world, Azerbaijani fairy tales, time, space, underground world.

Introduction

Azerbaijani fairy tales are traditional stories passed down by the Azerbaijani people. They cover a range of topics, including the heroic history of Azerbaijan and its struggles against both local and foreign oppressors. These tales also convey spiritual, moral, social, and philosophical perspectives. They serve as a means of preserving ancient national traditions and customs, while also showcasing the natural beauty of Azerbaijan, such as its lush valleys, majestic mountains, flowing rivers, and vibrant gardens.

The chthonic world in Azerbaijan fairy-tales: time and space is dedicated to one of the most significant issue in the Azerbaijan folklore study. The concept of time and space plays a crucial role in characterizing the chthonic world as a phenomenon, revealing mythical perceptions of a three-part structure, particularly focusing on one of its essential zones—the underworld or chthonic space in all its diverse manifestations.

In traditional Azerbaijan mythology, the chthonic world is portrayed as a complex space, presenting numerous challenges in the study of Azerbaijan mythology. Folklore materials, as well as fairy tales depict the chthonic world not as a unified entity. Unlike the clearly defined heavenly realm, the chthonic world in folklore can take various forms, such as the realm of the dead, graveyards, and specific places imbued with such significance—threshing barns, caves, meadows, and forests. This diversity in representation makes it challenging to pinpoint the exact location of the chthonic world. For instance, in the “Tale of Jirdan”

The folklore material further complicates matters by blurring the lines between the chthonic space and objects perceived as entrances to this space, acting as intermediaries between the tangible world and the chthonic realm. This ambiguity makes it difficult to characterize the chthonic space in terms of its visual, symbolic, and mythical aspects, influencing the interactions of chthonic characters within it. For a more accurate understanding of the chthonic world, it is essential to focus on its representatives—heroes, creatures, spirits, and deities who inhabit or symbolize it. These entities provide insights into the nature of the chthonic

world, shedding light on its characteristics in terms of time and space.

In the context of this article, the term “space time-chronotope” is a fundamental concept, derived from the combination of “time” and “space.” Additionally, terms such as “chthonic space,” “scenery of the chthonic space,” and “the chthonic world of the dead” are crucial for denoting the phenomenon under investigation. Perceptions that provide insights into the chthonic world are rooted in Azerbaijan mythology and ancient religious beliefs, with relevant information being extracted from folktales.

Drawing from fairy tales, the chthonic space can be categorized into two forms. One represents the chthonic world as the realm of the deceased, while the other signifies a space where a symbolic trial takes place—a hero can journey into this space and return to the world of the living as a living individual. In this context, the act of travel, specifically the motif of traveling, becomes a significant element, illustrating how the hero arrives at an understanding of the chthonic space and time. The majority of Azerbaijani fairy tales revolve around the theme of travel, providing insights into the chthonic world and its elements.

While investigating Azerbaijani fairy-tale texts, such factors are considered:

1) representation of the chthonic space in the text (underworld, the world of the dead etc.);

2) chthonic symbols (forest, Land of Fires, cabin in the forest and other symbols assumed to be chthonic);

3) chthonic characters, creatures, representatives (spirits, animals etc.).

It's important to highlight that the concept of the chthonic space manifests as a powerful and expressive mythical element, embodying ancient perspectives on themes such as death, life, initiation, and other significant events within this framework of understanding and insights. It is a widely and successfully used research method in folklore. Folklore researcher J. Meletinsky (М.Е. Мелетинский) indicates that this methodology

of analysis allows to expand the studied texts into functional groups - stylistic, storyline and mythical groups (Мелетинский 1977, 153).

Vladimir Propp's analytical framework for Russian folktales relies heavily on structural elements, but it falls short when disregarding the importance of functional symbols. When examining the initiation theme and the significance of travel within the context of chthonic space, Propp's functional scheme proves valuable in identifying consistent elements. However, when exploring the chthonic world and its characters, the scheme may not always be applicable, particularly when dealing with the realm of the dead. Propp himself acknowledges that these schemes can be reversed, and not all fairy tales adhere strictly to the prescribed structure.

While Propp asserts that entering the chthonic world is an integral part of fairy tales, there are instances where this process is omitted or the concept of the chthonic world is portrayed ambiguously, making it challenging to interpret its specifics or location, especially in symbolic terms such as meadow or forest instead of underground. Propp's fairy-tale analysis is structured around comparing tale structures, but his categorization often leans towards structural elements, neglecting the significance of function symbols highlighted by scholars like V. Turner and B. Malinowski. As a result, a structural functionality method can be employed, drawing from the rite theory in folklore and ethnology. Additionally, a deconstructive approach proves useful when dissecting the text for its deeper meaning. V. Propp's analyses corresponds with Azerbaijani fairy tale analyses.

The term "chthonic world" originated from Greek mythology, referring to the realm beneath the earth. It was introduced into Azerbaijan research in the 20th century. Although the term "chthonic" itself may not be used, the concept is integral to understanding Azerbaijan mythology. In contrast, scientific research in other countries often employs the term "Underworld" more frequently than "chthonic space."

In view of the available base of fairy-tale material, there are raised five variants of division:

- 1) the chthonic space as an underground cave, 2) the chthonic space as a specific place in certain situations on the ground, in an inhabited village area, 3) the chthonic space as a definite place in the heavenly space, 4) the chthonic sea, 5) unclassified location.

The primary focal point in fairy tale motifs for the comprehensive representation of chthonic space localization lies in the underworld and various subterranean forms. This underworld can encompass both the conventional human living spaces and distorted environments, characterized by their fantastical beings and realities, often emphasizing their non-existence in the real world.

Chthonic space localization patterns are closely tied to places within the human living space. A notable feature is the absence of clear references leading to the underworld; the journey into this space is portrayed as random. Surface space chthonic elements are commonly found in structures like castles, towers, forests,

lakes (or islands surrounded by water), houses, and cabins in the woods.

While the localization in heavenly space is complex, within a specific context, the celestial realm becomes an expressed chthonic place. This localization is often symbolized by features like the glass hill, mound, or hill, where either the deceased enter or activities analogous to the chthonic place occur. In fairy-tale motifs, mountains can serve as both petrification sites and testing grounds. Similarly, mountains and the sky play significant roles in folk songs and beliefs.

Another crucial aspect is the chthonic sea, which holds significance not only as a primordial creation place but also symbolizes the chthonic space—a realm outside of conventional time and space. Unspecified parts of the chthonic space in fairy tales can be situated anywhere, such as Azerbaijan lands serving as a realization of chthonic space or the transformation of a hero into stone as the chthonic space localization of the stone.

A crucial element to consider is not just the mystical landscape itself, but also the road leading to it. In many fantastical scenarios, the manner in which the protagonist enters the mystical realm plays a pivotal role in establishing the location's significance within the broader world framework.

An essential aspect to contemplate is not only the enchanting realm itself but also the path leading to it. In numerous fantastical scenarios, the protagonist's entry into the mystical realm holds significant importance in establishing the location's relevance within the broader world framework.

The road follows a fundamental structure: A (beginning) - B (destination) - A+ (return to the starting point, albeit transformed). This expedition serves as both a catalyst for and a reflection of the hero's mental and physical growth. Notably, various types of transformation, including death, are regarded as motivations for such journeys.

The structural breakdown categorizes characters in the chthonic space into distinct groups based on their functions:

Chthonic Deities: This group includes entities like giants, the devil, and various creatures.

Chthonic Animals and Other Characters: This category encompasses beings like the toad, spirits, and other zoomorphic forms.

Spirits of the Dead: This group consists of ghosts and small entities with unique functions not covered in the previous categories.

It is crucial to differentiate representatives in the chthonic world based on their functions. The analysis of fairy tales breaks down as follows:

- **Assistant/Savior Function:** Characters fulfilling the role of providing support and expertise in the chthonic space when needed. This function can be attributed to a wide range of characters, including deities, chthonic animals, and others, except for the devil, which primarily serves as a counterforce or trickster.

- **Injurious and Counterforce Functions:** Characters in this category play roles that are harmful or counteracting. The devil is particularly dangerous, but other

characters, such as the toad or snake, may also fulfill similar functions.

- Mediator Functions: This category poses challenges, as mediators are creatures capable of moving between at least two parts of the world, like between the ground and the underground. In Azerbaijan mythology, creatures like the horses, snakes and certain birds are associated with mediator functions, especially evident in fairy-tale motifs. For instance, in the tale "Tapdig", "Malikmammad".

In the initiation fairy-tale motifs, the expression of chthonic space is remarkably diverse. The distinguishing features of chthonic areas, where the hero undergoes the initiation process, can be outlined as follows: Chthonic spaces can be situated anywhere in the mythical world; It is possible for the hero to return after completing the given task; Chthonic spaces are typically non-lethal; the hero, aided by magical assistants, overcomes challenges and returns successfully; Time is distorted within chthonic spaces, and upon the hero's return, the effects on the system may or may not persist; The visual representation of chthonic space also varies based on the gender of the character undergoing initiation. Female initiation emphasizes ethical qualities like kindness and wisdom, while male initiation is characterized by battles.

There are different types of initiation, including traditional single-person initiation and dual initiation, where both the protagonist and a chthonic world character undergo the initiation process. Another form is incomplete initiation, where the process remains unfinished, leading to distorted time and space upon the hero's return. Such tales are relatively rare and can be associated with shamanic initiation.

The portrayal of chthonic landscapes in initiation tales is extensive, providing a broader description of the chthonic world. The diversity in modeling chthonic space makes initiation tales unique and contributes significantly to the understanding of this phenomenon within the broader context of fairy-tale motifs.

The alteration of time systems constitutes a highly intricate and challenging phenomenon within the realm of the mythical world. Understanding the temporal dimension of the mythical world holds particular significance, especially in the context of initiation fairy tales, for several reasons:

If spatial distinctions outweigh temporal disparities in all alterations of the mythical world, the time system can be more precisely delineated. Particularly in motifs of initiation fairy tales, time is directly manifested. The narrative reflects changes in time analogous to the measurement of days and hours. In exceptional instances within fairy tale motifs, time undergoes deformations. For example, when the hero returns, the world has undergone transformation.

When a fairy tale or folklore hero enters the mythical world, they are immersed in a distinct temporal framework. Therefore, time becomes a crucial factor signaling the hero's presence in the mythical world. Analyzing scenes from initiation fairy tales reveals that temporal shifts are most prominent in those connected to broader journeys through the mythical world and, notably, those intertwined with death. Moreover, such

shifts are integral to shamanistic initiation, where the hero experiences a transformative process as part of transitioning to a different social status.

This suggests that changes in the time system metaphorically represent the mental transformations undergone during the initiation process. The individual is altered, modified, and transformed, and these changes are symbolically linked to distortions in time within fairy tale narratives. The restructuring of time occurs not only when the hero enters the mythical world but also when the hero undergoes personal changes or transforms into another form. Moreover, the transformation process is a central characteristic of fairy tales, involving spatial and physical changes that are more explicitly depicted in motifs, while time, as an abstract concept, is embedded in the symbolism of objects and processes.

The concept of chthonic space, particularly when viewed as the realm of the deceased, can be examined through two key aspects: the "time-absence of time" and the "space-anti-space." The former explores variations in the perception of time within different systems analyzed within chthonic space realizations. In this context, time is considered in relation to its absence or altered nature.

The "space-anti-space" aspect involves the representation of creatures and spirits within chthonic space. It emphasizes that entities themselves remain unchanged by definition, while their properties and functions may undergo transformation. It's crucial to differentiate between chthonic space in wonder-tales, where heroes venture for various reasons with the intention of returning, and the chthonic world of the dead. In the latter, the number of characters is limited.

In Azerbaijan fairy tales, the chthonic world of the dead lacks a specific definition, allowing for a broader range of localization sites and forms. The chthonic space type is defined by its unique time system, distinguishing between the time related to human life and the time associated with the world of the dead. This temporal framework can be characterized as the presence or absence of time. The coexistence of various world times is connected through the concept of time-space, yet a more detailed examination reveals distinctions between them. In the first scenario, time progresses linearly, while in the second, time stands still. In fairy tales, the absence of time frequently appears in scenes where the deceased beckon the living to join them in visiting the world of the dead.

The chthonic space-time system, as outlined in this thesis, emphasizes the concept of "absence of time," representing time that does not unfold cyclically but remains stagnant. In folk stories, the absence of time is marked by immobility, contrasting with the depletion, loss, burnout, and entanglement associated with time in the world of the living (e.g., a burning candle, a loud noise, a yarn thread tangling). It is not just a different kind of time; it is the absence of time, a state where time does not progress or exist.

Examining the folklore representations of the chthonic world of the dead, the concept of "absence of time" emerges as a comprehensive characteristic. However, there are instances where the absence of time transforms into a semblance of time, especially when

the chthonic world of the dead intersects with the living world, introducing a conditional flow of time. The time system in the world of the dead, viewed as the location of the deceased, is influenced by the time of the living world, shaped by the characters' perspectives.

The analysis of the time system in the chthonic space proves challenging, given the mythical worldview where time functions differently, if at all. Time is not clearly defined in these texts, making it difficult to draw insights and conclusions. The folklore texts suggest that time has ceased to exist in the chthonic space of the dead, presenting an opposition to the earthly time system and the model of absence of time. While our chronology relies on units like day-night and year, these measurements lose significance in the realm of folktales. Chthonic time essentially embodies the absence of time, manifesting in visible deformations of the temporal system within fairy tales, emphasizing that time, as we understand it, does not exist in this context.

The creation of the world, as depicted in mythical narratives, is explored through both cosmogonic and aetiologic myths. Cosmogonic myths are more overarching, while aetiologic myths delve into specific aspects. In Azerbaijani folklore, cosmogony involves a dynamic interplay between forces, namely God and the devil, who engage in both conflict and cooperation while shaping the world. Creation myths serve to provide archaic humans with a sense of place, purpose, and the perception of nature as a divine creation, fostering an awareness of the sacredness of the natural world. In essence, cosmogonic and aetiologic legends address the origin of the world by emphasizing the involvement of two sacred beings and the interaction of two worlds.

Characteristic of cosmogony and anthropogony is a dual creation myth, wherein both heavenly and chthonic forces play a role in the creative process. The dual creation myth stands as one of the oldest concepts in Azerbaijan folklore, persisting with some modifications over time. In the context of mythical narratives, the chthonic space is viewed as a source of the origin of the earth and humanity. The term "chthonic" takes on a broader meaning, encompassing primitive forms of existence and serving as an analogue to origin. This is evident, for instance, in the portrayal of the chthonic world of the dead, where individuals not buried in a proper tomb, ensuring revival, are consigned to a chthonic equivalent of origin—a swamp. The perceptions of the world's origin are rooted in its chthonic genesis, highlighting the collaboration of opposing dual powers, where one is a celestial being and the other a chthonic deity.

Conclusion

In summary, this article explores the enduring elements of the chthonic in modern society. It is concluded that the chthonic world and its entities manifest in various forms within contemporary culture, both traditionally, maintaining their original imagery (as seen in graveyard culture and chthonic creatures), and in modified ways (such as the transformation of chthonic spaces). Specific chthonic elements have found adaptation within different subcultures, particularly within the gothic subculture. Characters from the chthonic realm,

akin to elements of folklore in general, emerge prominently in society during phases linked to social crises and periods of transformation. It is noteworthy that during such times, society attempts to symbolize its negations, recognizing that established public institutions—be they religious or secular—are often inadequate in addressing public concerns. Consequently, society seeks alternative avenues for responses in these situations.

The chthonic world stands out as an intricate phenomenon, posing crucial questions in Azerbaijan folklore research related to defining chthonic space, pinpointing its location, and understanding the distinctions between its spatial forms and the structure of the temporal system.

In Azerbaijani fairy tales, the chthonic space exhibits diverse forms, making it challenging to establish a unified system. While functional characteristics define certain forms, such as the chthonic space in initiation tales and the realm of the dead, there exists a division between the sacred middle and the chaotic, profane surroundings. Each form of the chthonic world establishes its unique center-side division.

Folklore genres introduce variations in the depiction of chthonic space, with fairy tales offering the broadest and most unique descriptions. A comprehensive understanding of chthonic space emerges when comparing it across different folklore genres like folk songs and beliefs. Wonder tales and fairy tales encapsulate key attributes of chthonic space, showcasing its diverse locations within the mythical world. Entry into the chthonic space may be intentional or unintentional, often driven by the pursuit of extraordinary knowledge.

Deities, spirits, and chthonic animals serve as representatives of the chthonic space, offering vital insights. The symbolism associated with these entities reflects aspects of chthonic space, such as dangers, its connection to its role as the world of the dead.

Azerbaijani fairy tales provide specific perceptions of the chthonic space, expanding visual and temporal descriptions. The chthonic world of the dead is characterized by terms like space-anti-space and time-absence of time. It exhibits complexity in spatial and temporal structures, featuring areas frozen in time and others, like cemeteries and forests, facilitating connections with this world.

The chthonic aspect is present in cosmogonic motifs, where the initial state of the world created by the demiurge is chthonic chaos. The creation process involves a deity shaping the world and a devil influencing the primary source. Myths about the chthonic world persist in contemporary society, manifested as chthonic elements. These elements, borrowed directly from folklore or adapted in various ways, play a role akin to a carnival in popular culture.

In summarizing various aspects of the chthonic world, it becomes evident that it is characterized by ambiguity and temporal variability. This is particularly observable in fairy tales, where there is a departure from the conventional hero-fight-counterforce structure. Instead, the chthonic space and representational characters align with the cultural norms of the time. Chthonic space takes on an ominous and perilous nature, capable

of exerting influence and posing threats. The heterogeneity of chthonic space is also influenced by folklore genres and scenes. The chthonic space from which the hero returns in initiation texts differs from the chthonic space where they exist as a spirit.

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